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Mustapaqulov S.U. Texnik mexanika fanini o'qitishda talabalarning texnologik kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ahamiyati	213
Nafetdinov Sh.Sh., Ochilova M.A., Sultonova N.O'. "Tuproqning morfologik belgilari" mavzusini o'tishda klaster metodidan foydalanish	216
Narbekova R., Narbekov F. The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught	219
Nazarova N.G. Pragmatik kompetensiya talabalarning xorijiy tildagi kommunikativ kompetensiyasining strukturaviy komponenti sifatida	222
Nazarova Yo. The role of intercultural competence in foreign language teaching	224
Nematova N.M. Animatsion yondashuv asosida talabalarga rus tilini o'qitish texnologiyasi tizimi	226
Norova B.Yu. Interactive educational technologies in the teaching foreign language	228
Rozibaeva D.A. Technology of teaching agricultural terms	231
Ruzmetova M.A. Features of teaching english language on the basis of distance learning	233
Saydaliyeva M.A. O'quvchilarning ingliz tilida og'zaki nutq kompetensiyasini shakllantirishga mo'ljallangan mashqlar va topshiriqlar tizimi tahlili	235
Sharapova G.Sh., Rasulova M.I. T Interference of mother tongue in learning English	238
Sharopova Z.F. O'zbek tilini sohalarda qo'llanish bo'yicha talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish tizimi	241
Turdiyeva K.U. The importance of innovative technologies in learning foreign languages	243
Tursunova F. The main aspects of the formation of socio-cultural competencies of students in foreign language classes	245
Tuychiyev A. O'yinlar vositasida o'quvchilarda intizomli munosabatni shakllantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	247
Umarova F.N. Modern methods for the development of communicative competencies of the english language of students in the engineering union	250
Umarxodjayeva D.M. The role of independent work of students in the teaching a foreign language	252
Usmonova M.S. Texnologiya fani mashg'ulotlarini samarali tashkil etishda interfaol ta'lim metodlaridan foydalanish	254
Xojaniyazova B.M. Effective methods of teaching english in non-philological areas	257
Xoliqova L.F. Filologik ta'lim yo'nalishlaridagi talabalarning tadqiqot qobiliyatini (PBL) loyiha asosida o'rganish metodining samaradorligini aniqlash	260
Атаев У.Э. Инновационные методы и технологии учебного процесса на уроках русского языка в школах с узбекским языком обучения	262
Ахмадова Ч.Б. Ёшларни фаол жисмоний ривожлантириш жараёнлари	265
Бобоходжаев Р.Х. Характерные особенности лингвистических задач студентов на основе информационного моделирования	267
Бурхонова С.Т. Значение преподавания истории в учебных заведениях	269
Исматова М.Ш. Мустақил таълимда "очик-ёпиқ саволлар" коучинг моделларидан фойдаланиш	271
Майдырова А.Б., Таджиева С.У. Цифровая грамотность – как фактор повышения человеческого капитала преподавателей ВУЗов	274
Махкамova M.Ю., Арипова Н.А., Холмаматова Л.А., Турдибекова Р.Ш. Об актуальных проблемах подготовки современного творческого педагога дошкольного образовательного учреждения	277
Нишонov У.И., Парпиева М.М. Инновационные решения для преподавания русского языка в высших технических учебных заведениях	281
Саттарова С.Н., Марупов Ш.Н., Аллаярова Д.К. Кредитно модульная система в ВУЗах	284
Сулайманова Н.Дж. Междисциплинарная связь феномена оценивания	287
Ташкенбаев Т.Т. Прагматический аспект целей обучения русского языка как иностранного языка в технических вузах	289
Халмаматова Л.А., Курбанова Н.Б., Ходжаева С.А. Профессиональные качества руководителей в сфере образования	292
Худойбердиева А.Х. Условия развития творческого мышления младших школьников в инновационной образовательной среде	295

Achieving the educational goal of practical classes in English also involves the search for effective, innovative methods, means and forms of education. Teaching English is aimed at developing the ability of Uzbek students to communicate fluently in the target language in oral and written form, to read and understand technical, popular scientific and socio-political literature in English, to write correctly, to be able to work with technical dictionaries, to understand the meaning of technical texts, perform an accurate translation of texts on agricultural topics, comprehend what they read. Teachers should, with the help of a special organization of the educational process and new techniques, increase students' cognitive interest. Already in the first or second year of an agricultural university, it is advisable to offer students not only reproductive tasks, but also partly search exercises. Let us give an example: read three fragments, find and write out the words-terms, arrange them in alphabetical order.

1) *Soil acidity* - a property of the soil, due to the predominance of hydrogen ions over hydroxides in the soil solution, exchangeable hydrogen and aluminum ions in the soil absorbing complex.

2) *Chemical soil reclamation* - a set of measures aimed at improving its agrochemical, agrophysical and biological properties through chemical ameliorants - lime or gypsum.

3) *Organic fertilizers* - various organic substances used as fertilizers (manure, manure, green manure, peat, etc.)

As a result of using partially search tasks, Uzbek students acquire deeper knowledge in their specialty, successfully learn English for special (professional) purposes, develop skills that allow them not only to communicate fluently in English in oral and written form, but also to read and understand the content of texts, work with technical dictionaries, educational and scientific texts, understand agricultural terminology necessary for future professional activities.

Thus, the process of teaching Uzbek students of agricultural terminology in English should become purposeful and systematic, the training of specialized terms will be organized taking into account the profile of their future professional activity. In this case, the problem of increasing the efficiency of teaching Uzbek students of agricultural terminology will be successfully solved.

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FEATURES OF TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE ON THE BASIS OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada masofaviy ta'lim asosida ingliz tilini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari yoritib berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *masofaviy ta'lim, xorijiy tajriba, ingliz tili, innovatsiya, pedagogik qobiliyat, pedagogik mahorat.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье освещаются особенности преподавания английского языка на базе дистанционного обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *дистанционное обучение, зарубежный опыт, английский язык, инновации, педагогический талант, педагогическое мастерство.*

Abstract. *This article highlights the peculiarities of teaching English on the basis of distance learning.*

Keywords: *distance education, foreign experience, english, innovation, pedagogical skills, pedagogical skills.*

“Distance education” or as it is also called - distance learning, is engaged in open-type universities that receive funds for development from the state and are located far from North America. Such training uses a number of radio, television, and modern computer technologies, and programs for higher distance education have already been developed in thirty or more countries around the world. The development of distance education in Europe dates back to the seventies of the last century, when a number of open universities were created for distance education.

Today, every country in Europe has educational institutions that are engaged in the implementation of distance learning programs, the methods of which are developed at a professional

level. The greatest interest in training is caused by programs that use the latest information technologies, computers and multimedia, satellite digital television and network technologies. In modern pedagogical concepts, learning ceases to be considered only as a process of transferring knowledge from the teacher to the student. The defining trend of modern education is the transition to a person-oriented education system.

Modern telecommunications in distance learning provide a more interactive way of learning compared to distance learning. Students' contacts with the teacher are interactive. In order to study effectively in the distance education system, some initial knowledge and hardware and technical support are necessary.

The purpose of distance learning of foreign languages is to provide students in educational institutions of higher professional education with the opportunity to master basic and additional educational programs directly at the place of residence or temporary stay. Telecommunications are the main link in the distance learning system, which allows for maximum spatial and temporal independence of students and teachers. The system of distance learning of foreign languages differs from traditional forms of education by its high dynamism, due to the flexibility of the choice of training courses, a large amount of independent work, a variety of forms of educational and methodological support, which makes it possible to dramatically increase the effectiveness of educational processes regardless of the place of residence of students. In recent years, three types of distance learning based on:

1. Interactive television (two-way TV);
2. Computer telecommunications networks (regional, global), with different didactic capabilities depending on the configurations used (using text files, multimedia technologies, video conferences);
3. A combination of CD-ROM technologies and the Internet. The most common method of organizing distance learning involves the use of computer telecommunications in the form of e-mail, teleconferencing, other information resources of regional networks, as well as the Internet.

Distance learning has revolutionized the way language learning takes place, including English language teaching. By leveraging technology, it has become easy to provide high-quality English language instruction via distance learning. Some of the key features of teaching English on the basis of distance learning include:

1. Flexibility - Distance learning enables students to learn English at their own pace and on their own schedule. This allows them to balance their studies with work and other commitments. Flexibility is one of the most significant benefits of distance learning, especially for non-native English speakers who want to learn English. With distance learning, students can learn English at their own pace and according to their own schedule. This allows them to balance their studies with work and other commitments, such as family responsibilities or social activities. As a result, students can achieve their language learning goals without having to sacrifice other important aspects of their lives. By taking advantage of the flexibility that distance learning offers, students can improve their English proficiency and advance their careers in a way that fits their unique lifestyle and needs.

2. Accessibility - Since distance learning can take place online, learners from any part of the world can access quality English language instruction, provided they have an internet connection. Distance learning has proved to be a boon for English Language learners across the world. With online classes becoming increasingly popular, anyone with an internet connection can access quality English language instruction. This has enabled people from remote areas to learn and improve their language skills. The best part about this mode of learning is that learners can access the course of their choice from any part of the world, without having to relocate to a different place. This has made learning English more accessible and facilitated an increased interest in the language. Online distance learning has become a popular method of instruction. One of its advantages is accessibility. Anyone with an internet connection can access high-quality English language instruction. This is ideal for those who live in remote areas or cannot attend traditional classrooms due to disabilities or other issues. Distance learning provides an opportunity for all learners, regardless of their location or circumstances, to learn English and improve their communication skills. With the flexibility of online learning, individuals can adjust their learning schedule to fit their lifestyle, making education more accessible than ever before.

3. Personalization - Distance learning allows English language teachers to cater to the individual needs of learners. This means that learners can receive personalized attention, which can lead to more effective language learning outcomes. language skills with other learners from diverse backgrounds. Distance learning is a boon for English language teachers as it enables them to provide personalized

attention to learners as per their individual requirements. This personalized approach leads to more effective language learning outcomes. Students get the opportunity to improve their language skills with other learners from diverse backgrounds, which enhances their overall understanding of the language. Distance learning is proving to be an immensely effective way of teaching English, and is likely to continue to grow in popularity in the years to come.

4. Multimedia content - The use of multimedia content such as videos, podcasts and interactive exercises can make the learning experience more engaging and immersive for learners. Incorporating multimedia into learning materials, such as videos and interactive exercises, can certainly make the experience more captivating and enlivening for students. Podcasts, for instance, offer an avenue to listen to material that might otherwise not be as captivating. At the same time, videos can offer moving images and animations to introduce concepts or illustrate complex processes, while interactive exercises allow learners to apply what they have learnt in a more engaging and immersive way. All of these multimedia elements can ultimately help learners retain knowledge better as they become more invested in the learning experience.

5. Collaborative learning - Many distance learning platforms offer opportunities for learners to collaborate with each other, even if they are geographically dispersed. Collaborative learning is a key component of many distance learning platforms. Learners are given the amazing opportunity to collaborate with their peers despite being miles apart from each other. This form of learning has proven to be highly effective as it allows learners to practice their English language skills in an engaging and interactive way. The ability to work together on tasks and projects helps learners to develop communication and teamwork skills, while also allowing them to learn from each other's unique perspectives.

Distance learning has changed the face of education. Teaching English through distance learning is an innovative way to bridge the gap between students and teachers. Distance learning has brought a great revolution in the world of education. By adopting the mode of teaching English through distance learning, the connection between students and teachers has become stronger. It is an amazing technological advancement which has enabled the students to get access to quality education while being at their home. Online learning has made the process of learning more flexible and convenient. It has opened up new avenues for learners who want to study and attain knowledge without any physical barriers.

Teaching English through distance learning is an effective way to improve English language skills. With its flexibility and interactive approach, it is a popular choice among students worldwide.

Teaching English remotely has emerged as a highly effective method to enhance one's English language skills. The convenient and flexible nature of this mode of learning has made it a preferred choice among students across the globe. Additionally, the interactive approach adopted by virtual learning platforms not only makes learning English interesting but also more engaging.

The popularity of remote English teaching has skyrocketed in recent times as it offers an incredibly effective way to improve one's English language skills from the convenience of one's own home. Its flexible and adaptable nature has made it a leading choice among students worldwide. Furthermore, the interactive and engaging teaching methodology embraced by virtual learning platforms makes learning English enjoyable and an enriching experience.

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O'OUVCHILARNING INGLIZ TILIDA OG'ZAKI NUTO KOMPETENSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHGA MO'LJALLANGAN MASHQLAR VA TOPSHIRIQLAR TIZIMI TAHLILI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada boshlangi'ich sinf ingliz tili darslarida og'zaki nutq kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish uchun mo'ljallangan mashqlar hamda topshiriqlarning turlari va ularning samarali usullari o'rganilgan. Chet til o'rganishda og'zaki va yozma nutqiy mashqlar ahamiyati tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: boshlangi'ich sinf, og'zaki nutq, kompetensiya, mashq, topshiriq